

Exploring Alternative Sources of Financing Secondary Schools in Nigeria for Sustainable National Development. A Study of Secondary Schools in Kogi State Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study was carried out to explore alternative sources of funding secondary schools in Nigeria, a study of secondary schools in Kogi State, Nigeria. The study discussed the concept of Education financing, the concept of secondary school, importance of finance in the management of schools, available sources of fund for secondary schools, and the limitation of these sources. It also discussed reasons for alternative sources of funding in secondary schools in Kogi state; The study identified alternative sources of funding secondary schools to include special education co-operatives, reinvigorating private sector participation in funding education, the establishment of community schools, and direct investment by secondary schools and aid from donor agencies.

Key Words: Education, Financing, Education finance, alternative sources of financing, Secondary schools, Kogi State.

Introduction

Education is crucial to the development of individual, societies, and nations. So many approaches have been proposed and implemented for the purpose of improving its provision and management at all levels in Nigeria. Some of the approaches according to Ogonnaya (2013), include the introduction of Education Tax Fund (ETF) in tertiary institutions across the country to help in the provision of infrastructures, the establishment of the Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF) to help in staff development and other areas of needs, deregulation of the sector to ensure private sector participation in the sector, introduction of the home grown programme in primary schools and curriculum revision from time to time to ensure that the educational goals do not deviate from national goals etc. The past two decades have witnessed an emerging and growing agitation by stakeholders in the education industry towards the propagation of alternative sources of funding secondary education in Kogi state to further improve the provision of quality education in the state. Funds are needed in secondary schools in Kogi state to help in the provision of classrooms, recruitment of teachers, the capital cost of workshop laboratories, libraries, lecture halls and theatres to further strengthen the education system which has been on the decline. This makes the issue under discussion relevant.

Kogi State, Nigeria

Kogi state is one of the thirty six states in Nigeria located in the North central region of the country. The state is inhabited by the Igalas, the Igbiras, The Okun, the Bassa and the Yoruba speaking people. The state has two hundred and fifty secondary schools spread across the twenty one local government areas in the state was hitherto classified among the educationally disadvantaged states in Nigeria. The researcher observed that in this state, there are inadequate classrooms, poor facilities, late payment of salaries death of other supporting services, inadequate classrooms for students and inadequate office accommodation for staff. This call for attention if the state must meet up with her stated objectives of the provision of quality education to the people.

Concept of Education Finance

Financing refers to the act of providing money for a project (UNESCO, 2012). Education finance refers to the act of providing money for education. In the context of this work, Education Financing refers to the provision

and utilization of money for the management of secondary education. Finance is required in secondary schools for the management of stated educational goals, provision of facilities, recruitment of teachers, supervision of schools and payment of staff salaries, etc. In the utilization of funds, the school manager should ensure to guide against diverting money meant for a particular project to another project

In secondary schools in Nigeria and Kogi state, in particular, the fund is needed for capital and recurrent expenditures. According to Ochai (2012), capital expenditures are long term expenditure on durable goods and services like acquisition of land, building of classrooms and hostels and provision of ICT facilities, etc. recurrent expenditure, on the other hand, refer to expenditure that is incurred regularly for example expenditure on payment of salary, stationeries , and transportation, etc. This expenditure must be incurred if the school must be alive to her responsibilities. Therefore money has to be generated to ensure this.

The concept of Secondary School.

Secondary education is the education received after primary education and before tertiary education. It is an intermediate education received by students to prepare them for useful living in the society and admission to a higher institution of learning. The Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN (1988) National Policy on Education spelt out the objectives of secondary education to include promotion of cultural values and preparation for life. This type of education should be properly funded to achieve the laudable objectives stated in the National Policy on Education. Many sources of the fund have gone into financing secondary education in Nigeria. The major sources of funds as identified by Ochai (2012) include annual budgets, soft loans, external aids, fees and charges, donations, endowment, handicraft and petroleum trust fund, etc. These sources of funds even though available for utilization in secondary schools across the country and Kogi state have not been able to meet the ever increasing needs of secondary education. Hence other sources of funds are required if secondary schools in Kogi state must attain their stated educational goals. This further justifies the need for this study.

Importance of Finance in the Management of Secondary Schools

Financing secondary education will bring about access to education by all and sundry. Access to education is the ability of an individual to acquire education and all the benefits attached to it irrespective of tribe, religion or race. (Akpa, 2001). In Nigeria, most of the people live in rural area with low per capita income this limit access and the quest for quality education. Financing education will increase the supply of education and its provision to the rural area. The ability of the poor to have a quality education is therefore hinged on the amount of money voted for its provision.

Financing secondary education reduces the incidence of indiscipline among staff and students in secondary schools. In the view of Onwuka (2007), if lecturers are paid their salary on time and students are provided the necessary facilities and conducive learning environment as at when due, effective teaching and learning will take place. An adequate supply of money is, therefore, important in secondary schools as it brings about sustainable growth in the education sector. Agitations and the frequent strike will be on the decrease.

Finally, Education financing helps to reduce the level of illiteracy in the country Scumen (2007). Most people in Nigeria are illiterate and live in rural area. Financing education help in reducing illiteracy and its attendant problems like deviance, extreme cases of robbery and unemployment, etc. the result is national development.

Reasons for Alternative Sources of Financing Secondary Schools.

Alternative sources of funds are required in secondary school for the following reasons.

Most secondary schools are underfunded (Ogbonnaya, 2015). This inadequate funding has put secondary schools under stress, the death of equipment and facilities for effective teaching and learning. Alternative

sources of funding will enable secondary schools to procure the necessary facilities to promote teaching and learning in schools

Financing secondary education will reduce illiteracy, poverty and generate employment (Owoicho Akpa, 2001). Nigeria is a country where most people live in rural area with subsistence means of livelihood, little per capita income and ignorance. This has placed most Nigerians in a disadvantaged position in terms of money and the ability to pay school fees for their children. Alternative sources of the fund will make the provision of education available to these groups of people thereby reducing ignorance, illiteracy and improve employment.

Furthermore, in Nigeria, since the introduction of Universal Primary Education (UPE) and the Universal Basic Education (UBE), secondary school enrolment has increased. According to Fafunwa (1977), an increase in school enrolment calls for increased funding, subvention and grants to enable the school cope with the teeming population. The increase in enrolment without corresponding increase in funding has brought about the fragmentation of available space and facilities needed for effective teaching and learning. Hence there is need to look inward and outward for alternative sources of funding to enable secondary schools to cope with the increase in population.

Apart from the above factors, the cost of running schools also calls for alternative sources of financing secondary schools. In the view of Okpanachi (2010), in Nigeria, there has been a steady increase in the prices of commodity and services over the years. Secondary schools are not left out, the increase in cost and services is universal, and it affects every sector of the economy. The cost of running secondary schools has doubled. In the same vein, Nigeria as a third world country has an unfavourable balance of payment position as a result of low productivity. Most of the facilities needed in the laboratories are imported. This also adds to cost of running the school. There has also been strong agitation by school managers for an increase in the cost of services rendered in terms of increase in salary and wages in line with the experiences of the time. Alternative sources of funding are therefore required to close the gap.

There is the need for another stakeholder in the society to contribute to the funding of education. Education is a very costly venture that requires the co-operation of all (Alfa 2005). The expensive nature of education requires that other stakeholders who benefit from the output of education should contribute meaningfully to the growth and development of the education industry. The contributions from these stakeholders will bring about quality teaching and research that will further bring about quality output for national development.

Globalization and internationalization of businesses activities all over the world call for alternative sources of funding secondary schools (Oguche, 2011). Innovation in Education, online learning, the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), etc. has brought about the need for the provision of ICT facilities, electronic library, hardware, and software, etc. to quicken teaching and learning. Government alone cannot provide the needed fund and materials because of the huge financial involvement. The rapid changes in technology has posed huge financial commitment on educators that additional sources of fund is required to cope with these challenges,

Finally, the need for a flow of talents in certain fields, career opportunity and providing hope for an educational opportunity to the larger segment of the society call for alternative sources of financing secondary education. The process of educating a child is a continuous process, generation unborn need to be educated, skill and manpower required to lay a solid foundation for the future require adequate funding that only alternative sources of funding can provide.

Alternative sources of financing secondary schools in Kogi state Nigeria for sustainable national development.

The increase in enrolment witnessed in secondary schools, inadequately trained personnel, alarming rate of strike by teachers and riot by students, poor supervision of schools and the dwindling allocation of resources from the state government and other attendant problems facing secondary schools in Kogi state can be reduced if alternative sources of funds are explored and properly utilized for effective secondary school administration. This will bring about national development.

The following alternative sources of funding are suggested to complement the existing sources of funds.

- (1.) Special education co-operatives. Stakeholder in the education industry can come together to form special education co-operatives. This co-operative will enable them to pool their resources together to establish schools, provide facilities for the schools, recruit teachers and other management staff and carry out effective teaching and learning.
- (2.) The private sector should be further mobilized to increase the availability of funds. It is true that in Nigeria, the educational system is deregulated to ensure private sector participation, but the private sector is underutilized when it comes to education financing. Mobilizing private sector will help inject more money into the system and improve educational services.
- (3.) Establishment of community schools. Members of the community can establish a school and fund it. Schools are located in the community, and the community benefits from its output. The community should be properly married to the school in terms financing. Financing can come in the form of contributions from members of the community. They can also be involved directly in helping the school through direct labour and academic services to reduce cost.
- (4.) Direct investment: The school can invest in ventures like a shopping mall, catering services, and bakery on a continuous basis to generate income for the school. The gains from this venture can be used for the development of the school.
- (5.) Finally, the school can apply for assistance from donor agencies like UNESCO, UNICEF to finance her programmes in specific areas like the provision of ICT facilities, staff development research, and provision of infrastructures.

Conclusion

Alternative sources of financing secondary school are the only hope for sustaining secondary schools in view of the dwindling allocation from the government and the inadequacy of the conventional sources of fund to meet the ever increasing needs of secondary education in Nigeria. Stakeholders in the education industry should be ready to tap the available alternative sources and more that were not mentioned in this write up for sustainable national development.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Further studies should be carried out on the following topics.

- (1.) Towards improving the management of funds in secondary schools in Kogi state Nigeria.
- (2.) Measures to reduce the cost of funding secondary education for suitable national development.
- (3.) Strategies for raising additional funds for the improvement of infrastructure in tertiary schools in Nigeria.

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